

DESCRIPTION OF METHODS FOR DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of developing logical thinking skills in future teachers, the methodology for developing logical thinking skills in future teachers based on philosophical education, and the effectiveness of developing logical thinking skills in future teachers. Also, methodological aspects of developing logical thinking skills in future teachers based on philosophical education are analyzed.

Key words: pedagogical, theoretical and methodological basis, competence, improvement, technological, model, methodological system, logical thinking, skill, concept, judgment, motivational and axiological, cognitive, problem-based learning methods, interactive technologies.

Introduction

Adhering to the principles of developing logical thinking skills among future teachers is consistent with the intended objectives. To achieve this, it is necessary to ensure the effectiveness of thinking in fulfilling the educational, pedagogical, and developmental aims of the learning process. It is recommended to make effective use of business games in the program of practical classes. In this way, elements of high intellect and thinking are gradually formed in future teachers. During the games, prospective teachers analyze situations, break down problems into parts, develop methods and tools for finding solutions, carry out professional actions in accordance with practical activities, and introduce corrections to the results obtained.

Literature review and methods.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of developing logical thinking skills in prospective teachers, the methodology of developing logical thinking skills through philosophy education, and issues related to the development of such skills have been studied by scholars such as J.T. Dillon, J.D. Gobert, O.J. Lindberg, A.D. Olofsson, C.F. Conrad, O.V. Alikseyeva, E.V. Veselovskaya, N.A. Garulya, V.S. Yegorina, N.A. Kolmakova, M.M. Tesheva, A. Abduqodirov, M.Kh. Baybayeva, M.U. Qo'chqorov, J.S. Iskenderov, Z.T. Nishonova, F.A. Rahmatova, G.A. Nazarova, and D.F. To'xtasinov.

Results and discussion.

Classifying problems according to forms of logical thinking allows for the identification of main ideas, their practical application, and their transformation into reflexive skills. The presence and logic of steady thinking (concept, judgment, inference), such as analysis, synthesis, abstraction, comparison, generalization, classification, and other operations, as well as the mastery of underlying rules and principles, indicate intellectual maturity. For students to grasp this during practice, it is necessary to provide examples of learning materials where these logical processes are fully implemented or applied integratively. From this perspective, the educational process aimed at developing logical thinking skills in teaching demonstrates the following distinctive advantages:

- a) stimulates students' interest in the learning process;
- b) encourages active participation of every student in learning;
- c) influences each student's emotions;
- d) creates opportunities for effective mastery of learning materials;
- e) provides multidimensional impact on students;
- f) enables feedback;
- g) fosters the formation of ideas, attitudes, and creative experiences;
- h) develops students' life and professional skills;
- i) facilitates behavioral changes among students.

The methods and technologies for developing logical thinking skills are directed toward meeting students' educational needs. In particular:

1. The content of the process of developing logical thinking skills should be related to the professional knowledge needs of future teachers, taking into account students' individual capacities, perspectives, and knowledge levels.

2. In the process of developing logical thinking, students gain additional confidence in their own abilities, acquire universal values, and develop a sense of responsibility for their learning activities.

3. Through training and business games, students consistently succeed in determining their positions, as group work requires them to defend their views with determination. As a result, students adopt collective decisions in agreement with group members and develop skills for working as a cohesive team, showcasing their abilities.

4. In the process of developing logical thinking skills, students independently reveal new abilities and actively acquire professional qualities.

5. Students systematically master the skills of applying the knowledge and professional qualities they acquire in their future careers.

6. The environment of goodwill, mutual trust, and cooperation created during the process provides favorable opportunities for intellectual growth and serves as a basis for the continuous development of students' cognitive abilities.

The process of developing logical thinking skills enables the organization of students' activities across different dimensions of education, including:

- Organizational dimension: conducting interactive sessions, trainings, discussions, business games, and press conferences;
- Activity-based dimension: identifying individual approaches to problem-solving, planning student activities, and organizing independent learning;
- Reflective dimension: analyzing errors, making corrections to plans and actions, etc.

Based on the ideas discussed above, it can be stated that the process of developing logical thinking skills is a special form of organizing and enhancing students' cognitive activities. During the learning process, students' collaborative activities provide opportunities for them to contribute to the assimilation of educational materials. They exchange knowledge, ideas, and action methods with one another. Such educational activities, carried out in an atmosphere of goodwill, create a favorable pedagogical situation for acquiring new knowledge.

The methods of developing logical thinking skills serve to: foster high-level professional inclinations; ensure the durability of knowledge; form strong intellectual activity among students; enhance communication skills; support students in achieving an active life-professional stance; nurture team spirit; prepare a basis for valuing individuality; allow students to express themselves freely; develop skills in emphasizing their professional activities; instill mutual respect; and shape democratic relations between students and faculty.

This, in turn, contributes to the systematic development of students' professional knowledge and competencies, modeling non-standard situations related to future careers, perceiving students as active participants in the pedagogical process, fostering a sense of responsibility for every action and decision, and teaching them to achieve success.

The process of developing logical thinking skills requires organizing the learning process in accordance with students' knowledge level, degree of mastery, educational resources, and didactic tasks. This presupposes adherence to the following pedagogical conditions:

- strengthening students' inclinations toward intellectual activity, fostering cognitive needs, and ensuring an environment of independence in the educational process;
- creating favorable opportunities for creative and logical thinking, accepting various ideas and opinions expressed by students with tolerance, ensuring their active participation, and instilling confidence in their ability to think innovatively while encouraging their creative activity;
- individualizing the learning process based on students' characteristics, needs, and intellectual potential;
- developing students' skills for working individually, in small groups, and collectively, expanding their creative potential, and encouraging them to adopt both standard and non-standard solutions to problems;
- selecting and applying interactive learning forms and methods that allow for the practical reworking and improvement of cognitive knowledge, which serves as the foundation for developing logical cognitive activity.

Teachers must be able to create the necessary conditions that foster the development of logical thinking skills in the process of designing and organizing pedagogical activities. Based on the results of empirical analysis, the process of applying methods and technologies to develop logical thinking skills can be divided into three stages:

Guiding stage.

At this stage, the preparation of participants and experts is carried out. Professors propose the working procedure, and together with students, the main goals and objectives of the lesson are developed, and the learning problem is formulated. Only after that are the common game rules described, and a package of information and materials regarding the course of the game is presented.

Stage of preparing the interactive teaching process.

At this stage, situations, constructions, rules, and other materials are studied in detail. The professor outlines the scenario of the lesson, game tasks, rules, roles, game processes, and procedures for calculating results. In consultation with the professor, students collect additional information, exchange views, and discuss the content and process of the game with one another.

Stage of organizing the lesson.

This stage represents the implementation of the lesson process. From the very beginning of the lesson, no one is allowed to intervene or make changes.

Only the leader may introduce corrections to participants' actions, and only if participants deviate from the main objectives of the lesson. The professor initiates the lesson, after which their main task is to observe students' actions and results, calculate their scores, clarify problems, and encourage students to assist one another in their work.

Discussion stage.

At this stage, the results of the learning situation are analyzed and evaluated. The teacher organizes the discussion process, during which experts present their opinions, participants exchange views, defend their perspectives and solutions, draw conclusions, share impressions, and talk about the ideas and difficulties encountered.

In designing the educational process, diagnosing the level of logical thinking development among students plays a crucial role. Therefore, this study paid particular attention to the following aspects of diagnosing intellectual abilities:

- First stage: Conducting surveys to identify students' knowledge and perceptions of logical cognitive activity, holding individual interviews to determine their understanding of pedagogical creativity, and analyzing the results of surveys and interviews.

- Second stage: Based on the results of the first stage, methodologies for developing logical thinking skills in future teachers are designed according to specific plans and programs, and ways of implementing them in higher pedagogical education are identified.

- Third stage: The level of logical thinking skills among future teachers is determined, and ways of applying these logical cognitive skills in pedagogical practice are demonstrated.

Conclusion

Overall, diagnosing the level of development of logical thinking skills among future teachers on the basis of diagnostic methodology and applying innovative approaches to teacher training has a positive effect on the effective development of their intellectual activity skills.

In conclusion, when designing the educational process, the development of logical thinking skills and the acquisition of logical activity experience among future teachers is closely related to the extent of their logical and creative skills.

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